

Environmental Difficulty Index for Endurance Running Performance

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Abstract

Weather conditions are often cited to be one of the most important factors in an athlete's performance in running, second to only training and preparation. This paper compiles the effect of various weather conditions, examining the impact of Heat, Humidity, Wet Bulb Globe Temperature, Solar Radiation, Wind, and Precipitation on performance. It also models the scale to which these conditions affect performance over differing distances. A quantitative examination of existing literature was performed, and the effect of each weather variable expressed as the percent change per 1 unit of said variable. Combining all these weather and scaling factors, this paper presents a unified model for the standardization of endurance running times across various weather conditions;

$$\Delta \%_{Total} = (M_{Thermal} \times M_{Wind} \times M_{Rain}) - 1.$$

Introduction

Anecdotally, athletes in running, and those analyzing, commentating on, and competing with them, at all levels point to the weather during their competitions as one of the greatest contributors to their success, or lack of, in their performance. With climate change, weather conditions will only continue to be more extreme [13], causing more variation in running performances. Despite the prevalence of weather impacting performance, there exists no method widely adopted method to standardize an athlete's time against either their own performances, or others', not in the same event or exact same weather conditions. This study aims to produce such a standardization algorithm, allowing athletes, coaches, commentators, and others, to directly compare the effects of preparation, motivation, equipment, or peak performance with an athlete's past performances, or the performances of other athletes.

Materials and Methods

To compile the effects necessary to produce a reliable algorithm, a literature search was conducted across Europe PMC, PubMed, PLOS, SpringerLink, SSRN, and Google Scholar to find studies relevant in producing the necessary data on weather effect on running performance. Studies were omitted if they produced non-quantitative results, did not include performance metrics, or did not examine the relationship between weather and performance. While peer reviewed articles were prioritized, the

research conducted by Green L., which is not peer reviewed, was used for added data in situations where peer reviewed quantitative estimates were limited.

Data Extraction

From each study performance metrics (such as time, speed, output) were analyzed in correlation with variables based on weather (temperature, humidity, WBGT, solar radiation, wind). From this data, each weather variable's effect on performance was assessed either directly from the existing literature or by analyzing regressions between given data points. This impact was quantified based on percent change per increase by one unit of the field. Temperature effect, and WBGT effects, were expressed as percent change per 1°C outside of the reported optimal range. Humidity was expressed as percent change per 1% RH outside of the reported optimal range. Precipitation effects were expressed as percent change per 1mm of rainfall. Wind effect was expressed differently, expressing the percent change per KPH of wind, broken into component vectors of headwind, crosswind, and tailwind.

Synthesis and Conflicting Sources

Due to deviation in literature, a narrative quantitative synthesis was used. In situations when different sources provided conflicting data, the median of the two sources was used in determining the percent deviation from the baseline optimal range. The median was chosen over the mean to reduce sensitivity to outlier estimates and large methodological differences between studies.

Scaling

The studies analyzed for the effect of weather on performance, they often focused on one particular distance, for running this was the marathon. Due to the fact that weather conditions will scale in effect with the amount of time spent in that weather, sometimes linearly, and sometimes nonlinearly, a scaling section was added in the formation of the running EDI. These scaling equations were based off literature relevant to how weather effects compounded with the time spent in that weather.

Results

Heat

While less useful for estimating running performance than a combined metric like WBGT, the temperature of the atmosphere still is one of the most important factors in determining the performance of a runner. The majority of sources analyzed present 5°C-15°C as an optimal range for

performance [4,5,9], which indicates $10^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ is the optimal air temperature for running performance. However, a slightly colder temperature, between 5°C and 7°C is more optimal for female runners [4,9], causing a reduction in the optimal temperature in the female equation from 10°C to a new calculated median of $8^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ as the optimal temperature for female runners. For every 1°C increase outside the optimal range, the time will increase by between 1:30 (1.5 minutes) and 1:47 (1.783 minutes) over the course of a marathon [2,4], with 1:38.5 (1.642 minutes) as median, and 2:00 (2.0 minutes) higher for every 1°C above 15°C [7]. Raw temperature penalties are treated here as locally linear approximations, and are not intended to model physiological responses outside moderate deviations from optimal conditions. For example, with Knechtle et al. reporting 580,990 finishers of the Boston Marathon, averaging a time of 3:36:25 (216.42 minutes) for men and 4:02:49 (242.82 minutes) for women [4], these time increases translate to a .76% and .68% increase in time across a marathon distance for every increase in degree above the optimal range for men and women respectively. Outside of 15°C , this causes a 0.92% and 0.82% increase in time for men and women respectively.

Humidity

Humidity is not the most effective measure for estimating true performance, and is cited in many studies [6,14] to only play a part in performance through altering the perceived temperature a runner feels. Mantzios et al. confirms with the low placement of humidity on the decision tree, accounting for only marginal impacts even with large swings in RH. With combined metrics accounting for RH providing a more complete picture of its impact on performance, and the lack of literature on its independent effect, relative humidity was dropped as a metric for determining the running EDI to ensure its effect was not doubly accounted for.

WBGT

Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT) is a combined metric for estimating the ‘true’ temperature a person feels in particular weather conditions [1,15]. The optimal range is presented as conflicting, with Mantzios et al. giving 7.5°C - 10°C as optimal, while Ely et al. gives 5°C and Knechtle to al. gives 0° - 6°C as the optimal WBGT range [1,4]. The average upper and lower bounds were calculated, yielding an optimal WBGT temperature between 4.17°C - 7°C , simplified to 4°C - 7°C . When WBGT remains under 10°C but above the optimal range, marathon time increases by 1.7% per $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for men and

3.2% per °C for women [1]. Outside 10°C, from 10°C-15°C times are 2.5% higher for men and 3.2% for women, between 15°C and 20°C times increase by 3.3% and 3.8%, and between 20°C and 25°C times increase by 4.5% and 5.4% [1]. To enable continuous modeling, percent penalties reported across 5°C WBGT intervals were converted into piecewise linear slopes by dividing incremental performance losses by the width of each temperature band, essentially distributing the performance loss evenly across each temperature band. For men, per degree penalties are as follows: when temperature is above optimal, but below 10°C there is a 0.34% increase per 1°C, 10°C-15°C has a 0.50% per 1°C, 15°C-20°C has 0.66% per 1°C, and 20°C-25°C has 0.90% per 1°C. Additionally, for each interval of 5°C, the previous interval is added on, meaning any percent change from 10°C-15°C adds 1.02%, from 15°C-20°C adds 3.52%, and from 20°C-25°C adds 6.82%. For women, the following are the penalties per degree; when temperature is above optimal, but below 10°C there is a 0.64% increase per 1°C, 10°C-15°C has a 0.64% per 1°C, 15°C-20°C has 0.76% per 1°C, and 20°C-25°C has 1.08% per 1°C. The interval additions are as follows: 10°C-15°C adds 1.92%, from 15°C-20°C adds 4.48%, and from 20°C-25°C adds 7.52%. There is less research available for the effect of cold temperatures, but there is an increase in time of 0.3% per 1°C below the optimal range [3], which will be used as a general cold effect.

Solar Radiation

Solar Radiation, reported as W/m^2 , reflects the amount and intensity of sunlight an athlete feels when competing. This sunlight intensity is namely affected by the time of year, time of day, and cloud cover [16], and influences heat stress by increasing core and skin temperatures [17]. As similar to relative humidity, solar radiation's effect on the performance of a runner is caused by influencing the 'felt' temperature, as well as its negligible impact on the physics of running [18], solar radiation was dropped as a metric for determining the EDI in favor of utilizing WBGT and avoiding double counting the effect.

Wind

Wind speed and direction primarily impact a runner's performance in two ways, via its cooling effect on the skin, and the mechanical effect wind has on slowing the runner down, or speeding them up [19, 20]. Similar to solar radiation and relative humidity, wind's cooling effect is accounted for in the WBGT metric, and therefore does not need its own quantification of effect, as this would result in a

double counting of its impact. In addition to cooling, the mechanical effect of wind plays a much larger role in the speed of a runner. Beaumont et al. presents the metabolic costs of running at different effective airspeeds, the combination of wind speed and runner speeds [10]. By using data from this study Table 1 was made, comparing the effective airspeed to the metabolic cost of running at that effective airspeed, with 100% being the metabolic cost of running in still air. Table 1 shows the relationship between effective airspeed and metabolic cost, while Figure 1 shows the derived equation to calculate the metabolic cost from effective airspeed.

Table 1

Wind Speed	10/km/h	12km/h	14km/h	16km/h
-20 km/h	94%	93%	92%	91%
-10km/h	97%	96%	95%	94%
0 km/h (Still Air)	100%	100%	100%	100%
+10km/h	108%	110%	112%	115%
+20km/h	120%	126%	135%	145%
+30km/h	132%	140%	142%	165%

Figure 1

$$\frac{C}{C_0} = 1 + k \left[\max \left(\left(\frac{v_r + v_w}{v_r} \right)^2 - 1, 0 \right) \right] - s \left[\max \left(1 - \left(\frac{v_r + v_w}{v_r} \right)^2, 0 \right) \right]$$

C/C_0 = relative metabolic cost

v_r = runner speed (km/h)

Where: v_w = wind speed (km/h), headwind > 0 , tailwind < 0

$k \approx 0.30$ (headwind penalty factor)

$s \approx 0.08$ (tailwind benefit factor)

From these metabolic penalties, we can calculate the effect on speed, by using Kipp et al., which reports an improvement in velocity of 2/3 (~67%) [12] the improvement in running economy (metabolic cost).

From this the equation in Figure 2 represents the change in marathon speed as a directly related to wind speed.

Figure 2

$$\% \text{ Change in Time} = 0.67 \times 100 \left[k \max \left(\left(\frac{v_r + v_w}{v_r} \right)^2 - 1, 0 \right) - s \max \left(1 - \left(\frac{v_r + v_w}{v_r} \right)^2, 0 \right) \right]$$

This equation represents the percent change from a direct headwind or tailwind, but when running in the real world winds do not often come as pure head or tailwinds, thus a way to determine the component must be determined. A vector of wind acting on a runner can be presented as a right triangle, with the hypotenuse being the velocity of the wind. If the vector comes from an air bearing from 0° to 90° from north, or from 270° to 360° from the running direction, the wind is a headwind, if the vector comes from an air bearing of 90° to 180° from the running direction, the wind is a tailwind. By converting the air bearing to a geometric angle by subtracting the air bearing from 90° and adding 360° if the result is negative. From this the headwind or tailwind component of any wind by finding the reference angle (α) and using the equation in Figure 3.

Figure 3

$$\text{Head/Tail Wind} = \text{WindSpeed}(\sin(\alpha))$$

By plugging in the head or tail wind components into the equation in Figure 2, the exact effect of any wind, from any direction, can be found for steady state endurance efforts, assuming the runner does not slipstream behind another runner, or encounter any changes in terrain or topography that would change the impact of the wind.

Precipitation

Precipitation is often anecdotally told to be the worst weather possible to run in and impacts many of the weather variables that affect performance. One of these is the evaporative cooling effect that rain on exposed skin has. This is included in WBGT and is therefore excluded from this section to avoid double counting. Additionally, falling rain can impact a runner’s performance [8]. The amount of precipitation was measured as the mm of rain fell over the course of the event. Knechtle et al. reports the effect of rain to be 0:44 seconds slower over the course of a marathon per mm of precipitation [11],

which, when analyzed in context of the average time shown in the study, 3:36:25 (216.42 minutes), reflects a percent change of 0.33% per mm. This contrasts with Green, who reports this as a change of 1:30 over a marathon, and using the study average of 230.5 minutes, represents a percent change of 0.65% per mm [7]. Averaging these figures gives an average of 0.49% increase in time per mm of precipitation. In addition to cooling effect and slowing effect of falling rain, precipitation also causes the running surface to accumulate with water, which produces a slowing effect due to slippage. Unfortunately, no literature was found that compared running times to surface wetness independent of actual rainfall. Thus surface wetness is incorporated in the 0.49% slowing effect of rain.

Scaling

All of the data presented thus far primarily applies to the marathon distance, however, weather effects often compound non-linearly with distance as more time is spent in the ambient weather conditions, thus changing the effect [3]. The base scaling, assuming all effects scaled in a perfectly linear way could be represented by the equation in Figure 4, where *Var* is the weather variable, *Baseline* being the percent change at marathon distance, and *D* is the distance of the event being solved for.

Figure 4

$$\Delta\%(D, Var) = \Delta\%_{VarBaseline} \left(\frac{D}{42.195} \right)$$

While non-linear scaling changes many weather variables, this does not apply to wind and rain, which act as mechanical forces on the runner, and thus do not exhibit super-linear scaling, expressed by the simple equations in Figure 5 and Figure 6

Figure 5

$$\Delta\%(D, Wind) = \Delta\%_{WindBaseline} \left(\frac{D}{42.195} \right)$$

Figure 6

$$\Delta\%(D, Rain) = \Delta\%_{RainBaseline} \left(\frac{D}{42.195} \right)$$

While many studies [2,3] report the non-linearity of weather impacts, none give definitive numbers for the exact exponents by which they change, thus, the following exponents are approximations based on what fits previous literature, and on what is observed in top level competitions. For air temperature an exponent 1.2 fits existing ultramarathon results and some existing literature [3] which demonstrate a super-linear relationship. WBGT is more complex, as it incorporates many variables. Specifically the effect of humidity appears to have a threshold effect at ~60%RH [21]. Below this threshold, the body can dissipate heat more effectively, while above this threshold, heating mechanisms begin to struggle, and thus a piecewise approach was used to define the effect of WBGT, using the average humidity across the event. The approximate equations for scaling are found in Figure 7.

Figure 7

$$\Delta\%(D, Temp) = \Delta\%_{TempBaseline} \left(\frac{D}{42.195} \right)^{1.2}$$

$$\Delta\%(D, WBGT) = \begin{cases} \Delta\%_{WBGTBaseline} \left(\frac{D}{42.195} \right)^{1.1}, & \text{if RH} < 60 \% \\ \Delta\%_{WBGTBaseline} \left(\frac{D}{42.195} \right)^{1.3}, & \text{if RH} \geq 60 \% \end{cases}$$

Final EDI For Running

After compilation of the literature percent changes for different weather variables were determined whenever possible, and approximate scaling equations were derived. As WBGT and Raw Temperature both serve to measure the same thing, WBGT is favored to find a truer effect of weather, but an equation without WBGT was also provided. Effectively, weather impacts performance in two ways, mechanically (Wind and Rain), and by influencing thermoregulation (WBGT and Temperature). To determine the final equation, a multiplicative equation was used to find the value of each multiple; M_{Heat} , M_{Cold} (If Needed), M_{Wind} , and M_{Rain} , where each variable is in the form; $M = 1 + \Delta \% (D)$. The final equations combining these is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8

$$\Delta \%_{Total} = (M_{Thermal} \times M_{Wind} \times M_{Rain}) - 1$$

Figures 9,10,11, and 12 show the thermal multipliers. The event mean WBGT, which should be used if available, and is mutually exclusive with raw temperature, thermal multiplier is as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9

$$M_{WBGTHeat} = \begin{cases} 1 + \Delta \%_{WBGTBaseline} \left(\frac{D}{42.195} \right)^{1.1}, & \text{if RH} < 60 \% \\ 1 + \Delta \%_{WBGTBaseline} \left(\frac{D}{42.195} \right)^{1.3}, & \text{if RH} \geq 60 \% \end{cases}$$

If a WBGT measurement is not available, an average raw temperature based multiplier is shown in Figure 10 for men and Figure 11 for women. However this less accurate than WBGT and should only be used if WBGT is completely unavailable.

Figure 10

$$M_{TempM} = \begin{cases} 1 + 0.0076(T - 10) \left(\frac{D}{42.195} \right)^{1.2}, & \text{if } 10 < T \leq 15 \\ 1 + 0.0076(5) + 0.0092(T - 15) \left(\frac{D}{42.195} \right)^{1.2}, & \text{if } T > 15 \end{cases}$$

Figure 11

$$M_{TempW} = \begin{cases} 1 + 0.0068(T - 8) \left(\frac{D}{42.195} \right)^{1.2}, & \text{if } 8 < T \leq 15 \\ 1 + 0.0068(7) + 0.0082(T - 15) \left(\frac{D}{42.195} \right)^{1.2}, & \text{if } T > 15 \end{cases}$$

If the temperature is below optimal, the equation in Figure 12 will calculate the time lost from such an environment.

Figure 12

$$M_{Cold} = 1 + 0.003 \times |T - 4| \left(\frac{D}{42.195} \right)^{1.2}$$

Wind and rain apply to the form $M = 1 + \Delta \% (D)$ All of the baseline effects are represented in Table 2 below.

Table 2

Variable	Units	Optimal Range	Penalty per Unit	Scaling Exponent	Sex-Specific
Air Temp (Above Optimal)	°C	5-15 (M) 5-7(F)	<15°: +0.76% (M) +0.68% (F) >15°: +0.92% (M) +0.82% (F)	1.2	Yes
Air Temp (Below Optimal)	°C	5-15	+0.30% when below 5°	1.2	No
WBGT Base	°C	4-7	Piecewise, see below	RH < 60%; 1.1 RH > 60%; 1.3	Yes
WBGT 7°-10°	°C	—	+0.34% (M) +0.64% (F)	RH < 60%; 1.1 RH > 60%; 1.3	Yes
WBGT 10°-15°	°C	—	+0.50% +1.02% (M) +0.64% +1.92% (F)	RH < 60%; 1.1 RH > 60%; 1.3	Yes
WBGT 15°-20°	°C	—	+0.66% +3.52% (M) +0.76% +4.48% (F)	RH < 60%; 1.1 RH > 60%; 1.3	Yes
WBGT 20°-25°	°C	—	+0.90% +6.82% (M) +1.08% +7.52% (F)	RH < 60%; 1.1 RH > 60%; 1.3	Yes
Wind	Km/h	0	Nonlinear: See Figs 2/3	1.0	No
Rainfall	mm	0	0.49%	1.0	No
Humidity	%	—	Excluded	—	—
Solar Radiation	W/m^2	—	Excluded	—	—

These equations as well as the percent changes from combine to form a unified Environmental Difficulty Index for running performance.

Discussion

Interpretation

The Environmental Difficulty Index equations previously presented give athletes, coaches, and spectators the ability to directly compare the training, pre-race preparation, and other factors that influence running performance. It allows the weather to be removed from a final race time, returning a time that would most likely be run in perfectly neutral conditions.

Limitations

As this is a compilation of data from other sources, issues do arise regarding the infallibility of the EDI due to gaps in the literature. Namely, the exponents used for scaling between different distances were only approximate, because of the limited research on the impact of weather with increased distance. Extreme weather events, such as torrential rain, extreme heat, or extreme cold, were included in the model, but likely influence performance more than shown by the EDI. The model also assumes an equal response to weather stress across all athletes, thus those who are better acclimatized will have their results inflated by the model. The crosswind component of a wind vector was ignored due to lack of qualitative evidence of its effect on running speed or metabolic rate. Additionally, wind gusts were also ignored by the model. Different clothing or footwear choices, which can alter thermoregulation and aerodynamic drag, are also not accounted for by the model. Drafting, changes in terrain, or variable pacing strategies all deviate from steady state endurance, and hurt the accuracy of the model. This focus on steady state endurance also means that the EDI produces absurd results for races less than ~1-2 miles, and very long ultramarathons. Lastly, due to the focus of the literature being on the whole finishing body of a race, this model likely does not work perfectly for elite athletes who are well above average fitness, or amateur athletes who are well below average fitness.

Applications

This model can be applied to many contexts, all of which would benefit from utilizing an adjusted time based on pure performance. For example, athletes can use this to have a better understanding of their times in relation to other athletes in the sport. Similarly, coaches and commentators can also compare the adjusted times of athletes to better determine how different athletes would perform in a “head to head” matchup. As the model can also work backward, the best time possible in certain weather conditions can also be calculated. This would allow athletes to see how they truly perform by inputting their own personal best, and calculating the EDI to give the theoretical best time an athlete could run in the given

weather conditions. Lastly the model can allow more simplistic collection of running data in real word environments. The use of weather adjusted time would allow simpler collection of data regarding the impact of equipment, motivation, preparation and training on running times, without trying to control for weather by using a simulated environment, e.g. a treadmill.

Future Direction

To greater improve the accuracy of this model, more research could be conducted regarding the impact of less studied weather effects. For example more research regarding the impact of more extreme weather, the impact of temperatures below optimal ranges, and the impact of crosswind would all greatly improve the accuracy of the adjusted time provided by the model. Further research concerning how weather effects scale with the time spent in the weather would improve the EDI accuracy for non-marathon events. The model could also be validated by conducting trials that validate the data provided by the literature, and verify the interaction between weather and time as suggested in the model.

Conclusion

The model presented throughout this study gives runners, coaches, commentators, and spectators a way to isolate an athlete's performance from the weather. By compiling existing literature into a unified, distance scaled framework the Environmental Difficulty Index allows for comparison across different events and locations by allowing the direct effect of preparation, equipment, training, and even mentality to be seen. Overall, the EDI allows one of the most commonly named factors and least quantified, in endurance running to be removed from a runner's time, letting the effect of other variables be seen more clearly.

Author Contributions

Aidan Rivera conceived the basis of the study, conducted the literature review, assembled the final mathematical model, and wrote this manuscript.

Funding

This research received no external funding

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest

Data Availability Statement

All data used in this study was sourced from publicly available research, and no new data sets were assembled

Ethics Statement

This research did not involve any human or animal participants, and thus needed no ethical approval

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